

Fibre Reinforced Silicon Carbide

E. Fitzer, R. Gadow

Institut für Chemische Technik
Der Universität Karlsruhe

The paper describes the methods of chemical vapour impregnation (CVI) and reaction bonding by liquid silicon impregnation for the fabrication of carbon fibre and silicon carbide fibre reinforced SiC. The chemical and physical bases for these processes are described and the resulting promising mechanical properties for different fibre-matrix combinations are discussed.

These combinations are in detail: polycarbosilane based SiC-fibre/CVI-SiC, polycarbosilane based SiC-fibre/RB-SiC, CVD-SiC-fibre/CVI-SiC, C-fibre/CVI-SiC, C/RB-SiC and refractory coated C-fibre/RB-SiC.

The chemical and mechanical stability of the inorganic reinforcement fibres in original state and at high temperatures, respectively after high temperature treatment, are described and principal considerations for the reinforcement of brittle materials with high modulus fibres are introduced.

The main subject are studies on the possible composite fabrication methods chemical vapour impregnation and bonding by the reaction of liquid silicon with an original carbon binder with defined microstructure. The theoretical aspects of the two heterogeneous reactions are shown as well as the processing of the composites. By the CVI-Process SiC-composites with a flexural strength up to 950 MPa can be obtained, where the Young's modulus is controlled by that of the reinforcement fibre. In the case of reaction bonding SiC-composites with 300...600 MPa and strain to failure of less than 0.2% result. With the exception of the CVD-SiC-fibre reinforced material they show multiple fracture behaviour with residual strength of 60...30% $\sigma_{g,max}$ at fivefold strain to failure.

By the reinforcement of SiC by carbon fibres relative stress intensity factors $K_{IC,rel}$ with values up to $10 \text{ MN/M}^{3/2}$ can be obtained, compared with $1.5\text{-}3.5 \text{ MN/m}^{3/2}$ for sintered and polygranular reaction bonded SiC.

The main advantage of these new SiC-composite materials are the improved fracture behaviour and the expected low creep rates.

